

Section : Research Summaries

[Sl.No.-2](#)

Medical Writer: Joydeep Bhattacharjee

mRNA Cancer Vaccine: Exploring Different Therapeutic Approaches.

Signaling a new epoch in cancer therapy:

After the success of two mRNA vaccines against COVID-19, research on their potential for cancer therapy has sparked widespread curiosity and interest. However, research and trials in this field have been ongoing since 1990.

The research and development of mRNA vaccines have gradually overcome numerous challenges in approaching personalized cancer antigens, with respect to structural modifications ensuring greater stability and antigenicity, and also by the introduction of advanced delivery systems to target specific cells and tissues.

In vitro transcribed (IVT) mRNA in these vaccines with codification of the target of interest (e.g, tumor antigen) is administered to the patient encapsulated in a special delivery vehicle like lipid nanoparticle whereby these mRNAs are uptaken by host cell, including antigen-presenting cells(APC) like dendritic cells or macrophages. The encoded proteins, e.g, tumor antigens, cytokines, etc., are synthesised from the mRNAs using cell machinery and presented by APCs to the T cells and B cells either in part or in intact form, thereby

activating a strong adaptive immune response against the cells expressing those proteins.

Exploring Different Therapeutic Approaches:

Targeting Tumor Associated Antigen (TAA) :

Tumor-associated antigens are generally over expressed in tumor cells as compared to normal cells, and this fact designates them as a prime target of cancer vaccines. Most of the vaccines tried to date, based on individual TAAs, have offered greater efficacy and reduced side effects.

Some of the common TAAs include carcinoembryonic antigen (CEA), alpha-fetoprotein (AFP), HER 2/ neu, melanoma-associated antigen (MAGE), prostate-specific antigen (PSA), etc.

Vaccine BNT III targeting four common TAAs (NY-ESO-1, MAGE-A3, Tyrosinase, TPTE) is exemplary. In over 90% of cases with cutaneous melanoma, BNT III induced novel and preexisting immune responses against these antigens. (Phase I trial, NCT04526899) A phase II trial is underway combining BNT III with Cemiplimab(anti-PD I antibody) for advanced melanoma patients unresponsive to anti-PD I therapy.

Limitation of therapy targeting TAAs is that, being a non-mutant self-antigen, they are a part of the self and thus can lead to poor T cell response and immune tolerance during the therapy. Also, as they are expressed in normal cells to some extent, the risk of collateral damage can't be overruled.

Strategies to overcome these challenges include delivering cancer antigen with immuno-stimulating molecules, enhancing

immunoactivation in the tumor microenvironment, and combining vaccines with radio or chemotherapy.

Targeting Tumor-Specific Antigen :

The mutation, abnormal gene expression, and post-translational modifications in cancer cells express proteins or peptides that are unique to the tumor cell and not found in normal cells. These proteins or peptides, known as tumor-specific antigens or neoantigens, are presented at the surface of the tumor cell through major histocompatibility complex (MHC) molecules. The tumor-specific property of neoantigens clearly establishes their suitability as targets for vaccine therapy without affecting normal cells, thus ensuring an excellent safety profile.

In 2014, Trans [et.al](#) successfully treated a bile duct patient with ERBB2IP-specific CD4+ cells, achieving complete tumor regression, demonstrating TSA's potential in inducing anti-tumor response. The researchers also found gene mutations in 9 out of 10 gastrointestinal tumor patients that indicate the widespread presence of tumor heterogeneity with TSAs varying among patients, even within the same tumor type.

The development of personalized mRNA vaccines involves the identification and selection of neoantigens through advanced sequencing and bioinformatic approaches.

Several clinical trials involving TSAs, e.g mRNA-4157 and BNT 122, the typical personalised vaccines, are underway. mRNA -4157 encoding a repertoire of 34 antigens targeting unique mutations in

individual tumor DNA, is undergoing clinical trials for melanoma, non-small cell lung cancer, and other solid tumors.

The abundance of neoantigens in many cancers, like pancreatic cancers, makes a neoantigen-based mRNA vaccine a viable therapeutic strategy.

Limitations targeting TSAs include under expression of neoantigens in some types of cancers. The tumors with a lower prevalence of mutation lead to lower expression of neoantigens, and in such cases, their identification and application of TSA-based therapy may be difficult or even impractical.

Another issue of concern is the cost and complexity of the TSA vaccine due to the uniqueness of the neoantigens of each patient and cancer type.

Supplementing mRNA-encoded immunomodulators :

Cytokines and co-stimulating ligands e.g CD 40, CD 70L etc., are crucial molecules that enable communication between immune cells and activation of antigen-presenting cells, mediating a robust immune response. The tumor microenvironment (TME) is characterized by limited T cell infiltration with an abundance of immune-inhibitory cells and thus puts up resistance to current immunotherapy.

The delivery of cytokines, co-stimulating ligands via mRNA can effectively remodel TME and enhance tumor sensitivity to various immunotherapy.

An escalatory vaccine mRNA -2752 encoding OX 40L, IL-23 and IL-36 gamma proinflammatory cytokines was investigated in solid tumors. A clinical trial for BioN Tech developed BNT-153 is also ongoing.

These cytokine-based products demonstrated promising results such as amplification of T cell response and decline in immunosuppressive effect in TME.

Targeting Onchogenic viruses :

Viruses like Human Papilloma virus (HPV), Hepatitis B, Epstein-Barr(EBV) , and HIV cause various cancers. Though the traditional therapy is vaccination as a prophylaxis, the mRNA vaccines offer a therapeutic approach by stimulating the body's immune system to recognise and attack cells expressing those viral antigens. A recent Phase I clinical trial of the mRNA vaccine eOD-GT8 60mer against HIV showed a good safety profile and induced broad neutralising antibodies in 97% participants, demonstrating the potential of mRNA vaccines in HIV prevention.

Other Approaches :

Monoclonal antibodies (mAbs) are now widely used for cancer immunotherapy. Many studies have shown that fully bioactive mAbs can be produced in vivo by delivering mRNA encoding such mAbs. Rituximab, a clinically approved IgG1 I that targets CD-20, is a classical example of mRNA-induced mAb. With rapid progress in this field, based on bispecific antibodies (bsAB) that form a bridge between tumor cells and T cell, provides another promising approach to induce anti-tumor activity.

Additionally, the delivery of mRNA encoding tumor suppressor p53 to liver cancer using nanoparticles showed promising results in patients co-treated with anti-PD-1.

End Note :

mRNA vaccine is thus a rapidly evolving field that has already achieved success in overcoming several challenges for effective cancer therapy. However, more in-depth research and trials will pave the way for promoting this innovative technology for cancer treatment.

References -

1. Recent progress in mRNA cancer vaccines

[Ruhui Yao](#)¹, [Chunyuan Xie](#)¹, [Xiaojun Xia](#)^{1,✉,P}

Pub Med Central.

2. mRNA vaccines in the context of cancer treatment: from concept to application Qiang Fu^{1†}, Xiaoming Zhao^{2†}, Jinxia Hu³, Yang Jiao⁴, Yunfei Yan³, Xuchen Pan⁵, Xin Wang^{5*} and Fei Jiao³

Journal of Translational Medicine.

3. Clinical advances of mRNA vaccine for cancer immunotherapy.

- Alexey V Yaremenko et al. Science Direct,2025

-

4. mRNA vaccine in cancer therapy: clinical advances and future outlook -Youhuai Li et al.

Clinical and Translational Medicine,2023

